

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**FREQUENCY OF INTERNAL HEMORRHOIDS IN PATIENT
WITH LOWER GASTROINTESTINAL BLEEDING
UNDERGOING COLONOSCOPY****¹Dr. Shahid Mahmood, ²Dr. Riaz Hussain Awan, ³Dr. Seema Nayab,
⁴Dr. Khadim Hussain Awan**

¹Consultant Gastroenterology and Hepatologist, ²Assistant Professor, Department of Gastroenterology, LUMHS Jamshoro, ³Assistant Professor, Department of Radiology, LUMHS Jamshoro, ⁴Resident, Department of Urology Sheikh Zayed Hospital Lahore

Article Received: June 2019 Accepted: July 2019 Published: August 2019**Abstract:**

Objective: To determine the frequency of internal hemorrhoids in patients presented with lower gastrointestinal bleeding undergoing colonoscopy.

Patients And Methods: The six months cross sectional study was conducted from 16 November 2011 to 15 May 2012 in the department of Gastroenterology, Liaquat National Hospital, Karachion patients presenting with lower gastrointestinal bleeding. History, examination and investigations were carried out. Then Lower gastrointestinal endoscopy was performed. Patient's information was recorded on proforma and analyzed by using SPSS-17.0.

Results: Total 203 patients were explored and the mean age of the patients was 43.06 ± 12.05 years (95%CI; 41.40 to 44.73). Out of 203 patients, there were 111 (54.7 %) males and 92 (45.3%) females, with 1.2:1 male to female ratio. Out of 203 patients, hemorrhoids was present in 76 (37.4 %) patients and it was the most common cause of lower GI bleed. Out of 76 patients, 35 (46.05%) were male and 41 (53.94%) were females. 60 (78.94%) patients had bright red colour while 16 (21.06%) patients had maroon colour blood. 24 (31.57%) patients had mild, 44 (57.89%) patients had moderate while bleeding severity was severe in 8 (10.52%) patients. Hemorrhoids were more prevalent in age group between 31 to 50 years of age

Conclusion: The frequency of internal hemorrhoids in all patients with lower gastrointestinal bleeding undergoing colonoscopy is high.

Key Words: Lower GI Bleeding, hemorrhoids, Lower GI Endoscopy.

Corresponding author:**Dr. Riaz Hussain Awan,**

Assistant Professor, Department of Gastroenterology, LUMHS Jamshoro.

Email: zulfikar229@hotmail.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Riaz Hussain Awan et al., *Frequency Of Internal Hemorrhoids In Patient With Lower Gastrointestinal Bleeding Undergoing Colonoscopy.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06[08].

INTRODUCTION:

Lower gastrointestinal bleeding (LGIB) is the bleeding from distal to ligament of Trietz & presents as bleeding per rectum.^{1,2}The acute colonic bleeding usually less severe and self limiting in some individuals but if severe or massive can be life threatening and responsible for mortality.³⁻⁵The common factors responsible for acute lower GI bleeding are non-steroidal anti-inflammatory medication and advanced age and use of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory (NSAID) drugs.⁶⁻⁷Diverticulae, angiodysplasia, malignancies, colonic inflammation, ischemic lesion, hemorrhoids and inflammatory bowel disease are common etiologies for LGIB world wide. In a study done in Pakistan showed that the annual incidence of LGIB has been estimated to be 20% and mortality as 11%.²Hemorrhoids are varicosities of the venous plexuses in the walls of the anal canal and lowermost 1.5-2 cm of the rectum. Internal hemorrhoids exist above the anal canal and the external are usually found beneath the skin and around the anus.⁸Haemorrhoids may present with bleeding, prolapse, pain, discharge and itching. The diagnosis of haemorrhoidal disease is made by proctoscopy, which allows confirmation in all cases. Internal hemorrhoids are classified into first, second, third, and fourth degrees, according to the size and amount of prolapse within the anal canal.^{9, 10}Haemorrhoidal grade is useful for therapeutic assessment,¹¹worldwide, the prevalence of symptomatic hemorrhoids is estimated at 5% of the general population.¹²Rationale of this study is that, although internal hemorrhoids are traditionally considered as the major cause of LGIB, no local study specifically addressing internal hemorrhoids has been reported. Therefore this study provides the burden of disease in patients with LGIB, which in turn can be utilized for planning purposes.

PATIENTS AND METHODS:

The six months cross-sectional study was conducted in Department of Gastroenterology at Liaquat National Hospital, Karachi. The inclusion criteria were age between 18-65 years, either gender, all patients with history of bleeding per rectum since six months were recruited while the exclusion criteria were subjects with inflammatory bowel disease, cirrhosis, bleeding diathesis, previous history of

haemorrhoids, history of surgery for the haemorrhoids, antiplatelet and anticoagulant, history of abdominal trauma, history of colonic cancer, family history of colon cancer, presence of weight loss and lower GI bleed secondary to upper GI causes.

The lower gastrointestinal bleeding: Blood loss per rectum (hematochezia) in the form of maroon or bright red blood or blood clots.

The Internal hemorrhoids: Visualization of dilated veins above dentate line in lower rectum during colonoscopy procedure on retroflexion maneuver.

All risks and benefits of colonoscopy were discussed with each patient and a written consent will be taken from the patient for inclusion in the study before the commencement of colonoscopy. All colonoscopy was carried out in a single visit. All procedures were performed by gastroenterologist fellows and consultants, fellows having at least two years experience in performing colonoscopies and were observed by a consultant having at least five years experience in colonoscopies. Finding was include the colour of bleeding and presence or absence of internal hemorrhoids. A structured performawas used and the data was collected on that prescribed proforma by the principle investigator.

Data will be analyzed in SPSS 17. Frequency and percentage was computed for qualitative variables like gender, colour of bleeding and hemorrhoids presence. To compare colonoscopic findings with colour of bleeding and other variables the chi square test was applied & the p-value ≤ 0.05 was labeled as significant.

RESULTS:

Total of 203 subjects presented with lower gastrointestinal bleeding and underwent colonoscopy for presence of hemorrhoids and other findings. The mean age of the patients was 43.06 ± 12.05 years (95% CI; 41.40 to 44.73). Out of 203 patients, there were 111 (54.7 %) males and 92 (45.3%) females, with 1.2:1 male to female ratio while the results are presented in Figure 1-5.

FIGURE : 1

FIGURE: 3

FIGURE : 2

FIGURE: 4

FIGURE: 5**DISCUSSION:**

The annual incidence for the rate of lower GI bleeding varies from 20.5 - 27 cases per 100,000 adult population at risk (0.03%) in the US.¹Johanson JF *et al*, evaluated analysis of 4 centers in US. and UK shown that prevalence rate of hemorrhoids is 4.4%.¹In our country different etiologies of bleeding per rectum, which differ from western world and raised the need for descriptive studies to reflect the true magnitude of the disease. The common etiology for bleeding per rectum in entire agegroups and in published series are hemorrhoids, ranging from 27 to 72% according to various authors.^{13,14}In earlier study 55% of patients had demonstrable hemorrhoids.¹⁵ In regards to acuteness and severity of bleeding per rectum a study shown that Internal hemorrhoids were responsible for severe bleeding per rectum in 14.2%,¹⁶ and Zuckerman et al in 1999 showed that haemorrhoids are the source of acute bleeding per rectum in 2-9% of patients.¹⁷In our study, 37.4% individuals presented with bleeding per rectum and had haemorrhoids. A former study demonstrated haemorrhoids followed by fissure-in-ano in entire age & gender.¹⁸In present series the male to female ratio was 1.2:1, which was similar to other studies as Van Rosendaal, et al¹⁹ had 1.2:1 and ShennakMM, et al²⁰ had 1.34:1 male to female ratio respectively. In present study the haemorrhoids (37.4%) are predominant factor for bleeding per rectum and is consistent with the study by Rhee and Lee.²¹ In

present study, patients with alarm symptoms other than per rectal bleeding (i.e history of weight loss, prior history or family history of colonic cancer) were excluded and I found that internal hemorrhoids was the commonest cause of bleeding per rectum especially in age group of 30-50 years. Internal hemorrhoids can be easily diagnosed by anoscopy (proctoscopy). So it is advisable that in developing countries where cost is a major issue, proctoscopy should be first investigation of choice in younger patients and patients having no alarm symptoms. Sigmoidoscopy and colonoscopy should be reserved for elder patients and for those having alarm symptoms. In our country, no local study specifically addressing hemorrhoids has been reported. A better understanding of the natural history of LGIB would allow identification of the exact frequency of internal hemorrhoids; therefore this study provides the burden of disease in patients with LGIB, which in turn can be utilized for planning and health strategic management purposes.

CONCLUSION:

Lower gastrointestinal bleeding is associated with significant mortality & morbidity. The frequency of internal hemorrhoids in subjects with lower gastrointestinal bleeding undergoing colonoscopy is high.

REFERENCES:

1. Johnsons JF, Sonnenberg A. The prevalence of hemorrhoids and chronic constipation. An epidemiologic study. *Gastroenterol.* 1990 Feb;98(2):380-6.
2. Zia N, Hussain T, Salamat A, Mirza S, Hassan F, Waqar A. Diagnostic Evaluation of Patients Presenting With Bleeding Per Rectum by Colonoscopy. *J Ayub Med Coll Abbottabad.* 2008 Jan-Mar;20(1):73-6
3. Barnert J, Messmann H; Diagnosis and management of lower gastrointestinal bleeding. *Nat Rev Gastroenterol Hepatol.* 2009 Nov;6(11):637-46..
4. Zuccaro G. Epidemiology of lower gastrointestinal bleeding. *Best Pract Res Clin Gastroenterol* 2008; 22(2):225-32
5. Barnert J, Messmann H.III. Medizinische Klinik, Klinikum A. Management of lower gastrointestinal tract bleeding. *Best Pract Res Clin Gastroenterol.* 2008; 22(2):295-312
6. Bernal JC, Enquix M, Lopez Garcia J, Garcia Romero J, Trullenque Peris R. Rubber band ligation for hemorrhoids in a colorectal unit. A prospective study. *Rev Esp Enferm Dig.* 2005;97:38-45.
7. Ali U, Samad A. Rubber band ligation versus open haemorrhoidectomy: *J Pakistan Med Institute.* 2005;19:317-22.
8. Randall GM, Jensen DM. Prospective randomized comparative study of direct current versus bipolar electrocoagulation probe for treatment of bleeding internal hemorrhoids. *Gastrointest Endosc.* 1994; 40: 403-10.
9. Jensen DM, Machicado GA. A randomized comparative study of bipolar electrocoagulation versus heater treatment of chronically bleeding internal hemorrhoids. *GastrointestEndosc.* 1997; 46: 435-43.
10. Pfenninger JL. Modern treatment of internal hemorrhoids. *Br Med J* 1997; 314: 1211-2.
11. Fukuda A, Kajiyama T. Retroflexed endoscopic multiple band ligation of symptomatic internal hemorrhoids. *GastrointestEndosc.* 2004; 59: 380-4
12. Majid A, Malik A, Butt MQ. Hemorrhoid's management by rubber band ligation. *Professional Med J.* 2006;13:664-8
13. Shinya H, Cwern M, Wolf G. Colonoscopic diagnosis and management of rectal bleeding. *Surg Clin North Am* 1982; 62: 897-903.
14. Goulston KJ, Cook Y, Dent OF. How important is rectal bleeding in the diagnosis of bowel cancer and polyps? *Lancet* 1986; 261-5.)
15. Caos A, Benner KG, Manier J, et al. Colonoscopy after Golytely preparation in acute rectal bleeding. *J Clin Gastroenterol* 1986;8:46-9.
16. Brackman MR, Gushchin VV, Smith L, et al. Acute lower gastroenteric bleeding retrospective analysis (the ALGEBRA study): an analysis of the triage, management and outcomes of patients with acute lower gastrointestinal bleeding. *Am Surg* 2003;69:145-9.
17. Zuckerman GR, Prakash C. Acute lower intestinal bleeding. Part II: etiology, therapy, and outcomes. *GastrointestEndosc* 1999;49:228-38.
18. Colacchio TA, Forde KA, Patsos TJ, et al. Impact of modern diagnostic methods on the management of active rectal bleeding. Ten-year experience. *Am J Surg* 1982;143:607-10.
19. Van Rosendaal GMA, Sutherland LR, Verhoef MR, Bailey RJ, Blustein PK, Lalor EA, et al. Defining the role of fiberoptic sigmoidoscopy in the investigation of patients presenting with bright red rectal bleeding. *Am J Gastroenterol* 2000; 95:1184-7
20. Shennak MM, Tarawneh MM. Pattern of colonic disease in lower gastrointestinal bleeding in Jordanian patients: a prospective colonoscopic study. *Dis Colon Rectum* 1997; 40:208-14.
21. Rhee JC, Lee KT. The causes and management of lower GI bleeding: a study based on clinical observations at Hanyang University Hospital. *Gastroenterol Jpn* 1991 ;26 Suppl 3:101-6